

Effects of ultrasonic assist on the solution properties of hydrophobically associating polyacrylamide

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Abstract : In order to study the effects of ultrasonic assist during the synthesis process on the solution properties of hydrophobically associating polyacrylamide (U-HAPAM), U-HAPAM was prepared by acrylamide, 2-acrylamido-2-methyl propane sulfonic acid, acrylic acid and octadecyl acrylate (ODA). The solution properties of U-HAPAM and control sample (HAPAM, without ultrasonic assist) were investigated through rheometer, laser particle size analyzer and AFM. The molecular structure of U-HAPAM was investigated by FT-IR. The results showed that the critical association concentrations (C^*) changed from 0.35 wt% (HAPAM) to 0.28 wt% (U-HAPAM), which was attributed to the well dispersion of ultrasound for ODA. Learned from laser particle size analyzer and AFM, U-HAPAM had stronger hydrophobic association than HAPAM. The novel method of preparation of HAPAM should be adequately attracted attention.

Keywords : Hydrophobic association, polyacrylamide, ultrasonic assisted polymerization, octadecyl acrylate, solution properties.

Introduction

Hydrophobically associating polyacrylamide (HAPAM) is the system that contains a major part of hydrophilic polyacrylamide backbone and a small number of hydrophobic groups (usually less than 2 wt%)¹⁻³. In dilute solution, intramolecular aggregates prevail over intermolecular ones, which make the macromolecular chains curled and hydrodynamics volume reduced. However, when the polymer concentration surpasses the critical association concentration (C^*), the intermolecular association takes place. This leads to a dynamic physical cross-linking network which makes the hydrodynamics volume increasing^{4,5}. Most importantly, there will be aqueous solutions with a substantial enhanced solution viscosity, which can be used well as stabilizers, fluidity control agents, enhanced oil recovery agents, paint thickeners and flocculants etc.⁶⁻¹¹.

Recently, many kinds of hydrophobically associating polyacrylamide were prepared with different synthetic ways or different hydrophobic monomers^{12,13}. The main method of synthesis of HAPAM was micellar copolymerization. In the micellar copolymerization process, the

hydrophobic monomer was solubilized within surfactant micelles, whereas the hydrophilic monomer was dissolved in the aqueous continuous medium. Francoise Candau¹⁴ prepared the hydrophobically-modified polyacrylamides by micellar polymerization, which had a complicated post-treatment of the product owing to elimination of large amounts of surfactants. Baojiao Gao¹⁵ prepared water-soluble associating polymer via a new micellar process using sodium 2-acrylamidododecane sulfonate (NaAMC₁₂S) as surfactant. They found that with the presented polymerizable surfactant NaAMC₁₂S, the micellar copolymerization could be favorably realized and complicated process to remove the surfactant was avoided.

Ultrasonic wave has dispersion and initiation/assisted initiation for radical polymerization because of acoustic cavitation. In ultrasound assisted initiation process, very fine and stable uniform monomer droplets are formed because of cavitation activity at/near interface of hydrophobic monomer phase causing disruption the later by micro jets. Further, the micro jets can transport the radicals towards the surface of droplets. Hesheng Xia¹⁶ studied a novel ultrasonically initiated *in situ* emulsion po-

lymerization approach in order to modify multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). The results showed that ultrasound had an excellent dispersion effect for carbon nanotubes in aqueous solution, and *in situ* polymerization of monomer BA or MMA on the surface of MWCNTs proceeded without any added chemical initiator successfully. Okudaira¹⁷ studied the suspension polymerization of styrene monomer, and the results showed that the reaction could be carried out without emulsifier and initiator under ultrasonic waves. However, very few literature of the ultrasonic assisted radical polymerization used in the synthesis of hydrophobically associating polymer was reported before.

Compared with some synthesis methods^{18,19}, the ultrasonic assisted radical polymerization method has dispersion and assisted initiation in the heterogeneous polymerization, even without surfactants used in micellar polymerization. In this paper, we report the results of our study on the effects of ultrasonic assist during the synthesis process on the solution properties of hydrophobically associating polyacrylamide (U-HAPAM) through FT-IR, rheometer, laser particle size analyzer and AFM.

Results and discussion

FT-IR :

The FT-IR spectrum of U-HAPAM had wide absorption bands at 3300~3500 cm^{-1} for the N-H stretching vibration. The characteristic stretching vibrations of C=O in acrylamide (AM) were shown at 1661 cm^{-1} . The absorption bands at 1116, 1042 cm^{-1} and 1408, 1558 cm^{-1} were for symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibration of the $-\text{SO}_3^-$ in 2-acrylamido-2-methyl propane sulfonic acid (AMPS) and $-\text{COO}^-$ in acrylic acid (AA), respectively. The peak at 1722 cm^{-1} was the characteristic stretching vibrations of C=O in ester, 1165 cm^{-1} was for C-O-C asymmetrical stretching vibrations and 1380 cm^{-1} was characteristic of $-\text{CH}_3$ absorption in octadecyl acrylate (ODA). The above data included all the characteristic absorptions of functional groups in AM, AMPS and AA, particularly, also showed that ODA was effectively introduced into U-HAPAM.

Critical association concentration :

As shown in Fig. 1, there was a remarkable difference in the viscosity change between U-HAPAM and HAPAM. Firstly, we concluded that the viscosity of U-HAPAM solution was higher. Then, by making the intersection of two different slopes²⁰, the critical association concentrations (C^*) were explicitly settled (0.28 wt% with

Fig. 1. Effects of copolymer concentration on the solution viscosity (ODA content : 1.0 wt%).

ultrasonic assist and 0.35 wt% with traditional micellar polymerization¹²), which indicated that the U-HAPAM had better properties of hydrophobic association.

Droplets of ODA were unstable in the reaction mixture and it was difficult for ODA to react with other comonomers. Because of the dispersion effect of ultrasound, the droplets of ODA were fine and stable and then ODA was easier to be introduced in U-HAPAM. As a result, U-HAPAM had higher solution viscosity and relatively lower C^* .

Effect of ODA content :

Effect of ODA content on the solution viscosity was shown obviously in Fig. 2. The impersonal data showed that, with rising of the ODA content in U-HAPAM, the viscosity increased because of growth in number of

Fig. 2. Effects of ODA content on the solution viscosity (Copolymer concentration : 0.4 wt%).

hydrophobically associating groups. However, when the content of ODA was over 1 wt% in U-HAPAM, the viscosity increased by a small margin (the content of ODA was only 0.6 wt% in HAPAM to reach this trend). Additionally, the viscosity of U-HAPAM was obviously higher than that of HAPAM, which was attributed to the more effective introduction of ODA in U-HAPAM. Learned from the results, the optimal content of ODA in U-HAPAM was 1 wt%.

Aggregates size analysis :

Fig. 3 showed the change of apparent average aggregate size (d^*) with increase of copolymer concentration. From the data, the obvious hydrophobic association oc-

Fig. 3. Effects of copolymer concentration on apparent average aggregate size.

curred in HAPAM when the concentration surpassed C^* (0.35 wt%). While in the U-HAPAM, the association occurred even the concentration below C^* (0.28 wt%), which indicated the stronger associative effect of U-HAPAM due to the effective introduction of ODA in U-HAPAM macromolecule.

Fig. 4 showed the aggregate size distribution of U-HAPAM with 0.2 wt% concentration (below C^*) and 0.3 wt% concentration (above C^*) separately. In the 0.2 wt% solution, the d^* was about 1017 nm. And when the concentration of HAPAM increased to 0.3 wt%, the d^* increased remarkably to about 2140 nm. The obvious change was due to the hydrophobically associating effect from intramolecules to intermolecules. This showed that the association models influenced the aggregate size distribution and d^* .

Fig. 4. The aggregate size distribution of U-HAPAM in aqueous solution.

AFM :

The microstructure of hydrophobically associating polyacrylamide solution could be directly observed by AFM, which was an effective supplement to the method of viscosity, fluorescence and so on. The images of HAPAM and U-HAPAM solutions were shown in Fig. 5.

Learned from the images, aggregate structures appeared both in HAPAM and U-HAPAM at the concentrations below C^* . At the same time, the associative structures of U-HAPAM were more than those in HAPAM. It presented that the degree of association of U-HAPAM was greater and it could form more and larger hydrophobic associative structures.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

AM, ODA, AMPS, AA and potassium persulfate (KPS) were all analytical grade and used as received without further purification. Distilled water was used for all experiments.

Synthesis of U-HAPAM :

A certain amount of AM, AMPS, AA, ODA and an appropriate amount of deionized water were added into a 250 ml beaker and was mixed by high-speed mechanical stirring. The mixture solution was purged with nitrogen for at least 10 min. After that, the beaker was put in an ultrasonic tank (Water temperature : 50 °C; Power : 150 W). The KPS solution was injected into the reaction mixture, and the resultant mixture was continuously reacting for 1.5 h. The product was gelatiniform and clear. It was

Fig. 5. AFM images : (a) HAPAM; (b) U-HAPAM (0.2 wt%).

directly dried under vacuum at 50 °C for 12 h and finally broken into powders. (Complicated process to remove the surfactant used in micellar polymerization was avoided¹²).

Measurements :

The infrared spectroscopy of the U-HAPAM was carried out through an FT-IR Bruker Model V70 (Bruker, Germany) with using ATR accessory. Before testing, samples were precipitated into a large amount of ethanol.

Data of average particle size was recorded from the BT-9300Z laser particle size analyzer. The samples were filtered with a 450 nm micron membrane before testing.

The rheological behaviors of the samples were measured through a Brookfield DV2III Ultra rheometer.

Atomic force microscope (AFM) observation was con-

ducted by WET2SPM2 9500J3 atomic force microscope (Japan island Jin).

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